

THE INTERPRETATION OF WOMEN'S SPIRIT IN THE STORY "ANCIENT SONG" BY ZULFIYA KUROLBOY'S DAUGHTER

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Abstract

In this scientific article, the inner experiences and psyche of Shahsanam, the main character in the story "Ancient Song" by our writer Zulfia Kuroloy, who became famous for her stories in today's Uzbek short story writing and skillfully embodied female characters in her stories, are analyzed.

Key words

Love, suffering, loneliness, psyche, desire.

The works written on the image of a woman and her spirit are among the works that are timeless and distinguished by their vitality in all times and places. The beautiful aspects of the image of a woman are revealed in Uzbek literature in the works of Miss Zulfia Kuroloy, Salamatkhan Vafoeva, Jamila Ergasheva and a number of other writers. In particular, we can see beautiful examples of a woman's image in almost all the stories of Zulfiya Kuroloy's daughter. Adiba, focusing on the image of a woman, creates her dreams, aspirations, goals, and psyche in a very impressive way. The story unfolds before the eyes of the reader. The story "Ancient Song" also depicts female characters, and the spirit of the character of the main character of the story, Shahsanam, greatly affects the reader and brings him pity. The main character of the story, Shahsanam, gets married as a second wife to Eshan, who treated her for her illness. The reason for this is not clear to anyone. Not long after that, Eshan died, and Shahsanam was left alone in the courtyard. Of course, this affects his mental health and well-being. "It's all... because I'm tight..." Shohsanam said brokenly. His face was saffron, his eyes were old, and his thin body was extremely weak. Shahsanam was fading day by day. The reason for her depression was that, on the one hand, she was alone, and on the other hand, her childhood love turned into a dream. Even so, the woman could not lose heart from her lover, living with him gave her happiness and encouraged her to live life. She also had the right to be happy as a woman. Sultan Murad, who encouraged the

lonely Shahsanam, gradually brought her back to life. "Every change in his state of mind did not go unnoticed by the young man: "Today he spoke for more than half an hour, he spoke calmly and without anger. Even his laughter began to ring out...". Unfortunately, this woman's happiness and joy will not last long. "Shohsanam woke up in the middle of the night from a thunderclap, and suffered an unbearably painful heart attack for twenty minutes, and... handed over his deposit."

If the reader is surprised by the thunder that struck the earth like a light despite the temperature being forty degrees, then he will feel sorry for the young man who left this world early because of that thunder. This event fills the reader with deep thoughts.

Nevertheless, whether these two lovers do not want to leave each other, or because this separation affected Sultanmurad very much, even after Shahsanam's death, he came to Sultanmurad's side: "The young man who passed by the window suddenly stopped 'xtadi. - You?! - Yes, I... - After all, you... - I couldn't go!" At this point, the writer Shahsanam explains why she does not want to leave this world, even though her soul has left her body, but she cannot leave this world: "The world is so beautiful! It's enough to live and breathe... How wonderful is the rustling of leaves in the moonlight... But... I love this world because of your presence. Because of you!" When Sultan Murad is about to commit suicide, Shahsanam appears in his eyes and tries to dissuade him by crying out to take him from this world. In this place, the writer talks about the death of Shahsanam, her helplessness, how she will suffer in the afterlife if she lives with Sultan Murad in this world, and if she leaves this world early and her late husband follows her, she will find happiness in the next world. Although Sultan Murad did not leave this world, his mind had completely left. That love made Sultanmurad mad and Shahsanam unhappy.

The work mainly depicts two female characters, one of them is Shahsanam, and the second female character is her relative and Sultan Murad's wife. The writer has described them in his own way. If Sultan Murad's wife is depicted as being interested in the lives of others and paying less attention to her husband, instead of paying attention to her husband and family, the image of Shahsanam is embodied as a kind and gentle woman to her beloved. It is no exaggeration to say that the creation of such contrasting female characters in the story ensured its effectiveness and vitality.

Zulfia Kuroloy was able to show the most delicate and intimate aspects of a woman's spiritual world through her stories. His stories are distinguished by their harmony with life events, without any exaggeration, and we would not be mistaken if we say that the writer held a mirror to life through his stories. At this

point, we can see that the following thoughts of Umarali Normatov are appropriate: "After Sister Saida, we have before our eyes a talented writer who exudes an elegant Uzbek sophistication and at the same time a brave courage and a sense of justice in her works. I consider it a happy event for our national prose. Indeed, Zulfia Kuroloy's daughter was able to show her talent in Uzbek literature and won a place in the hearts of readers.

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